

ISic1637

I.Sicily inscription 1637

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

natural rock

Object

painted rock face

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of S.Giovanni

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Catacomba di San Giovanni

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Superianus
2. cl[erecus] de
3. Aq[ileia] hic
4. reqescet

1. Superia
2. nus cle
3. recus de

4. Aqileia

1. Superianus

2. c[lerecusde]

3. [Aqileiahic]

4. reqe[scet qui vix]

5. et an[nos ---]

Apparatus

Text after Agnello 1953

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 493922

EDCS 12700065

Bibliography

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undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

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Cristiana*. 17: 43-81. At 55 no.6

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edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4354678>